
Communication Audit of Digital Entrepreneurship Academy of Human Resources Research Program and Development Agency of the BPSDMP Kominfo Surabaya in Pamekasan Region

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Abstract

The Digital Talent Scholarship (DTS) program by the BPSDM (Center for Human Resources Development and Research) Kominfo aims to enhance the skills and competencies of Indonesian human resources in the digital field. One such program is the Digital Entrepreneurship Academy (DEA) program, which trains individuals to accelerate the growth of digital technology in entrepreneurship. This study aims to understand the DEA Program training in Pamekasan Regency, conducted by BPSDMP Kominfo Surabaya, and its benefits. The qualitative research method used is interviews, observation, documentation, and literature studies. Results show that almost 100% of participants in the DEA program experienced success in business development through networking both offline and online. The study concludes that progress has been significant in the DEA Program training, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, which has shifted many activities from conventional to digital, including entrepreneurial activities. Monitoring is necessary to ensure the program's resources, expected outputs, and constraints. The research aims to provide an overview and study of digital entrepreneurship by the government to the community.

Keywords: DEA Program, Digital entrepreneurship; Training

Abstrak

Program Digital Talent Scholarship (DTS) oleh BPSDMP (Balai Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia dan Penelitian) Kominfo bertujuan untuk meningkatkan keterampilan dan kompetensi sumber daya manusia Indonesia di bidang digital. Salah satu program tersebut adalah program Digital Entrepreneurship Academy (DEA), yang melatih individu untuk mempercepat

pertumbuhan teknologi digital dalam kewirausahaan. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk memahami pelatihan Program DEA di Kabupaten Pamekasan yang dilakukan oleh BPSDMP Kominfo Surabaya dan manfaatnya. Metode penelitian kualitatif yang digunakan adalah wawancara, observasi, dokumentasi, dan studi pustaka. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa hampir 100% peserta program DEA mengalami kesuksesan dalam pengembangan bisnis melalui networking baik offline maupun online. Studi ini menyimpulkan bahwa kemajuan telah signifikan dalam pelatihan Program DEA, terutama selama pandemi COVID-19, yang telah mengalihkan banyak kegiatan dari konvensional ke digital, termasuk kegiatan kewirausahaan. Pemantauan diperlukan untuk memastikan sumber daya program, output yang diharapkan, dan kendala. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk memberikan gambaran dan kajian kewirausahaan digital oleh pemerintah kepada masyarakat.

Kata kunci: Program DEA, Kewirausahaan Digital, Pelatihan

Introduction

A company, organization, or institution is made up of multiple people, each of whom has different interests. Any interaction activity in a given context requires communication to occur because it is only through communication that it appears to have the ability to affect an individual's behavior. A communication audit, which is helpful for assessing the entire course of communication, is required to maintain the quality of the communication within an institution or organization (Sudarmanto et al., 2023). Comprehensive and methodical analysis, evaluation, and quantification of various communication-related aspects are all part of communication audits (Suwatno, 2019). Empirical evidence indicates that, despite the formulation of "perfect" internal communication policies, communication frequently fails to function as intended, necessitating the need for a communications audit. Organizational performance is anticipated to be significantly impacted by communication inefficiencies. Executives in the organization feel that regular reviews of internal communication procedures are necessary. Reviewing internal communication practises is the most suitable method for determining how effective they are (Hardjana, 2014).

Nevertheless, the idea of communication auditing did not take off right away, despite its significance. A small group of professionals did not begin using communications auditing until the late 1960s. The idea of communication auditing is thought to be unpractical, which explains its lack of acceptance. Since it entails a thorough analysis of every aspect of communication, such as the source, meaning and message, receiver, medium, process, impact, and context of the communication, a communication audit is regarded as complex. Therefore, using a combination of quantitative and qualitative research methods is necessary when conducting a communication audit.

Therefore the researchers are interested in looking into how communication audits can be conducted at government agencies of the BPSDMP (Center for Human Resources Development and Research) in one of its programmers, given the significance of communication audits that are not balanced with the level of awareness of experts. Because

this programme makes use of widely-used information and communication technology as well as the community. One programme under the Digital Talent Scholarship (DTS) initiative was introduced by the Ministry of Communication and Information Technology and is known as the Digital Entrepreneurship Academy (DEA) (Suyudi, 2022). In order to strengthen the digital economy, the programme was designed to develop human resources capable of quickening the development or application of digital technology in the field of entrepreneurship (Humas Kominfo, 2022). The Human Resource Research and Development Agency (BPSDMP), Global Tech Company Partners, Colleges, Local Start-ups, and the BPSDMP (Center for Human Resources Development and Research) collaborated to create the programme, which started in 2020. The program's primary goal is to develop a group of young entrepreneurs with the abilities and know-how to successfully use technology, information, and communication.

The DEA programme also requires to increase the number of MSMEs that are aware of and adept at using the digital world to advance their entrepreneurial abilities. In accordance with the Small Enterprises Act, as specified in the Regulation of the Minister of State for Corporations and Small and Medium Enterprises of the Republic of Indonesia Number 2, 2008, small businesses can become more resilient and independent through training and support from the government, business community, and other sources. This is also consistent with the topics covered at the November 2022 G20 Presidency, which included the Digital Economy as one of the pillars of Digital Transformation. It is therefore envisaged that Indonesia will be able to produce a large number of creative digital entrepreneurs thanks to the DEA programme.

The following are problems that can be developed using background information:

- 1) Does the previous training program's audit communication process appear to have proceeded smoothly? As a result of the program's success, the organisational communication process between the trainees and programme managers is crucial. If a communication audit has been conducted, has it been thoroughly reviewed to ensure that any challenges have a resolution?
- 2) How is the Digital Entrepreneurship Academy (DEA) programme in Pamekasan Regency's BPSDMP Surabaya training conducted in terms of communication audits?
- 3) What is the DEA program's training curriculum?
- 4) What are the advantages of the communication topics covered in the training programme at the Digital Entrepreneurship Academy (DEA)?

According to the research's background information provided above, the researcher concentrated on an issue pertaining to the Communication Audit procedure that took place during the Digital Entrepreneurship Academy (DEA) training programme in the Pamekasan Regency.

Literature Review

Communication Audit

Communication Audit, according to Joseph Kopec is the analysis of organisational communication both internally and externally to get a general picture of communication needs,

policies, actions, and capabilities. It also aims to identify the data required to empower management of the company to make decisions based on reliable and cost-effective information for the organization's future communication. This data is utilised for communication within the organisation in the future (Carter, 2007). It is necessary to conduct a detailed analysis of the company's communication practises, including what it says, how it says it, and who it says it to. Businesses are able to see what they are doing clearly in this way. Decisions or policies can then be made using the data audit communication.

An effective communication audit requires the following elements in order to function: 1) the person or people with whom the conversation should take place; 2) Specifically, with whom the conversation is held; 3) The things that ought to be expressed; 4) Guidelines for effective communication The actual method of communication (Quinn & Hargie, 2004).

Purpose of Communication Audit

Communication audit has its own goals and justifications, as previously discussed in relation to its definition and effective implementation. These include:

- 1) To ascertain whether and where there are benefits or drawbacks to communication in relation to the topic, sources, and channels of communication
- 2) By appropriately assessing interpersonal trust, it is possible to gauge the calibre of data and communication partnerships.
- 3) Locate networks of informal operational communication and contrast them with official channels of communication.
- 4) By contrasting these people with the roles they play in communication networks, you can learn about the elements that lead to the formation of information flow barriers and gatekeepers.
- 5) Recognise the various forms of constructive and destructive communication meetings and events, along with instances of each kind.
- 6) In order to specify the components, frequency, and quality of connections of communication at the individual, group, or organisational levels,
- 7) Provide some recommendations for changes or enhancements that ought to be implemented (Suwatno, 2019).

Communication Audit Approach and Model

It is very important to keep in mind that the approach and model to be used will depend on the goals of the communications audit, as outlined by the researchers above:

- 1) Conceptual approach: In the area of communication organisations, this approach addresses the effectiveness of communication systems or organisational performance. Setting criteria for evaluating the organization's performance, or gauging the degree to which the communication activities' aims and objectives have been met, is the first step in the process. Stated differently, it assesses the degree to which the organisation has met its objectives.
- 2) The most popular approach is the survey approach, which treats surveys as a single tool. Homophile research is one example of this methodology; it gauges communication effectiveness by comparing the transmitter and receiver's frames of reference.

- 3) The procedure approach gives the measurement tools' communication audit process top priority. This approach is complicated because it employs a team of auditors over an extended period of time who use a variety of measurement tools for the entire organisation (Suwatno, 2019).

In addition to the previously mentioned communication audit methodologies. Additionally, there are communication audit models that fall into the following three categories:

- 1) The conceptual structure model is an organisational communication audit that aims to comprehend the relationship between work procedures or implementation procedures such as the use of communication networks—the application of communication policies and their implementation, and organisational structure which consists of work units, functional communication networks, communication policies, and activities and the purpose or ultimate goal of organisational communication in order to achieve organisational goals.
- 2) The purpose of the organisational profile model, a functional analysis model of organisational systems, is to assess the current situation in order to identify errors that may be occurring within an organisation and devise solutions for them in order to improve organisational effectiveness.
- 3) Analysing and evaluating communication practises and activities in a particular context is part of the communication evaluation model. The data acquired can be used by management as a point of reference to enhance planning and control, as well as internal and external communication systems. Furthermore, it can assist in filling in the gaps that currently exist in communication systems (Suwatno, 2019).

Digital Entrepreneurship

Several things, including entrepreneurship, are now possible to do online because of technological advancements. Entrepreneurship is essentially the mindset of someone who conducts business or who is an entrepreneur; in other words, entrepreneurship leads to potential business activities (Munawaroh et al., 2016). The following strategies can help to overcome the challenges posed by digital transformation as an entrepreneur (Musnaini et al., 2020):

- 1) Create a thorough digital strategy,
- 2) Appropriate hiring practises for HR,
- 3) Sufficient utilisation of technology,
- 4) Real-time use of data,
- 5) Establishing efficient channels of communication between decision-makers and participants in the digital world is essential,
- 6) Applying the proper risk matrix.

Training

Training with maturity is necessary for the creation of optimal resources. The fundamental word exercise, which in KBBI means "learning and getting used to being able to (can) do something," is included in the term training. Thus, the process of training is the training itself. Training encourages people to develop new abilities for performing particular tasks and helps them understand the workplace. Consequently, it can be said that training is an endeavour

to broaden a person's knowledge and skill set so they can better adjust to their workplace. However, the community at large is not always included when discussing training for staff members (Willson, 2020). According to Siagian (1985, cited in Saktiarsih, 2015), the community can benefit from training in the following ways:

- 1) Assist the community in meeting its needs and improving its quality of life more quickly.
- 2) Enhance people's attitudes to help them adapt to changes in their environment and be able to make wise decisions.
- 3) Boost your innate desire to learn and develop a steadfast willingness to support the acquisition of new information and abilities.
- 4) The growth of a sense of self-worth and a stronger sense of unity within the community.
- 5) Boost output to a higher degree in terms of quantity and quality.
- 6) Shorten the average time it takes for people to pick up new skills and reach new performance levels.
- 7) Encourage loyalty, cultivate a positive outlook, and enhance teamwork.
- 8) Fulfil the prerequisites and standards of human resource management.
- 9) Lower the quantity and expense of workplace accidents.
- 10) Encourage and support each person's own personal development and progress.

Research Method

This study uses qualitative methodology, specifically by outlining fundamental presumptions and cognitive principles at the outset, and then employing systematic techniques for data collection and analysis to provide clarifications and arguments (Wijaya & Sirine, 2016). The process of conducting research using qualitative methodology produces descriptive data in the form of verbatim or written accounts of the subjects and behaviours seen (Riyadi et al., 2019). Since researchers are the primary instrument, a thorough understanding and analysis of field phenomena are required. Utilising a case study methodology, the research thoroughly examines, characterises, and describes individuals, groups, programmes or activities, organisations, or events that take place in society (Hariwijaya, 2016).

Data Collection Techniques

Observation

The purpose of this methodology is to gather accurate information about the Digital Entrepreneurship Academy Programme in order to develop human resources capable of accelerating the advancement and application of digital technology in the field of entrepreneurship and enhancing the digital economy. The DEA training facility in Pamekasan will be the subject of observations.

Interview

Muhammad Khusaeri, who oversees the DEA programme in the Pamekasan region, will be interviewed. The informant was picked due to his extensive background in managing the DEA program's operations in that location. More investigation into the DEA program's

communication process will be conducted with the help of these informants. Subsequently, data regarding the advantages of DEA training will be acquired from additional sources, specifically the trainees.

No.	Name/Initial	Position	Business Field
1	Muhammad Khusaeri	Commitee	-
2	MZ	Participant	Digital Printer
3	SD	Participant	Minimarket dan Souvenir Shop
4	DK	Participant	Catering Effort

Documentation

This context refers to a data collection approach that involves the examination and analysis of written materials, such as books, publications, regulations, and similar sources, among others. In accordance with the purpose of the research, (Mamik, 2015) states that it is essential to examine documentation pertaining to the implementation (DEA) by the Education Management Certification Fund Management Fund Management Agency (BPDSMP) Surabaya.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data Reduction

Data collected from observations, interviews, and documentation were chosen, focused on, and reduced in size. In order for the data to be in line with the research's focus that is, communication audits and the training advantages of DEA data reduction must be done.

Data Presentation

Presenting reduction data as comprehensive narratives and descriptions. Making decisions and taking action may become simpler as a result. To make data descriptions appear clearer, more detailed, and easier to understand, they can be enhanced with matrices, figures, tables, and other visual aids. The information provided includes participant benefits from DEA training and coordinator descriptions of activities.

Withdrawal of Conclusions

Analyse information about DEA implementation by BPDSMP Surabaya that has been gathered from documentation, observations, and interviews.

Result and Discussion

The purpose of this discussion is to present the results of research projects on the assessment of communication practises in the Digital Entrepreneurship Academy Programme at the Ministry of Communication and Information Surabaya's Human Resources Research and Development Agency, with a focus on the Pamekasan Region. The problem formulation and research focus previously described will serve as the foundation for the analysis. In addition to interviewing informants, researchers use these conversations to gather information and evaluate their findings, paying particular attention to issues and their solutions.

The effectiveness of the DEA program's implementation in terms of human resources is demonstrated by all of the DEA instructors, who have received training to enable them to address participants' needs and issues as they arise. This therefore has to do with how prepared they are to deal with issues as they arise. However, technological infrastructure can also experience issues from time to time, such as server outages, which can complicate registration for participants. Participants wanted DEA organisers to pay more attention (Pradinasari et al., 2023).

It is anticipated that DEA participants in this activity will expand their digital MSMEs both during and after the pandemic. Therefore, it is important to observe how entrepreneurs are adjusting to digital technology (Saktiarsih, 2015). The majority of participants, according to the interview results, could use the application to sell digitally but had not yet recorded financial statements. This is because the participants chose to manually record financial statements due to a variety of issues.

According to the information gleaned from the interviews, trainees in the DEA's ongoing training programmes face a number of challenges. The organisers, who are ultimately expected to solve the issue, are fully informed of these challenges (Adriansyah & Rimadiah, 2023).

Several factors contribute to the functional Communication Audit objectives being achieved. These include who communication should be conducted with, who specifically communication should be conducted with, what communication should be conducted, how communication should be conducted, and how precisely communication should be conducted (Quinn & Hargie, 2004). As the study's organiser, the Khusaeri informant should have received a description of the challenges faced by the participants. Based on the study's findings, it appears that the participants told the right person the informant Khusaeri about the challenges they faced. In terms of what needs to be discussed, participants should share the challenges they have faced. From the perspective of the ongoing programme, the training participants have established effective communication by communicating challenges like budgetary constraints and resource mismatches. Researchers can observe this when they speak with Khusaeri's informant, who manages the budget well to meet trainees' needs in the classroom despite a shortage.

It is obvious how communication needs to be conducted based on the research that was conducted. In order to assess the effectiveness of the material delivered, DEA training

providers offer Pre- and Post-tests. Informants have also mastered the use of internet platforms for business purposes, based on interviews with elementary, MZ, and DK informants.

However, the Communication Audit indicates that while this programme appears to be successful overall, there are still issues that need to be resolved. There are informants who continue to use manual methods, similar to financial statements that ought to be recorded digitally.

Conclusion

The primary objective of the DEA programme, which is run by BPDSMP Surabaya in Pamekasan, is to grow digital MSMEs, particularly in light of the COVID-19 pandemic, according to qualitative analysis that has been done. This is due to the fact that many activities, including entrepreneurial endeavours, have transitioned from traditional to digital platforms during the pandemic. In general, the program's implementation has been able to fulfil the requirements for carrying out training.

The challenges faced by trainees who have discovered solutions define this. For instance, instructors receive training to address trainees' concerns, particularly those related to registration. Then, although issues with technology infrastructure such as server outages and other issues with the internet have been resolved, problems still arise. The results of the interviews revealed that the budget was effectively managed to meet the needs of the trainees while also expeditiously achieving the trainee target.

However, the DEA programme Communications Audit found that the training program's implementation had not produced the best outcomes. Unresolved challenges that participants still face include manually handling financial statements.

Benefits of it frequently get received by different trainees. Furthermore, individuals have embraced digital technology to engage in digital entrepreneurship; however, some have refrained from utilising financial report applications because of a variety of issues. The participants' eagerness to grow their businesses and provide extra training based on individual needs then demonstrates their enthusiasm.

For the purpose of creating evaluative resources for an activity, conducting a communication audit is invaluable. In order to maximise the execution of public programmes, institutions and organisations' performance can be improved through the evaluation of programme activities, which also acts as a benchmark for gauging the programmes' efficacy. It's expected that the study will be a useful tool or point of reference for researchers working on similar communications audits in the future. Within academic research, particular attention is paid to auditing, communicating, investigating, and providing training. Several useful suggestions can be provided as follows:

- 1) Organisers of DEA programmes are required to participate in communications audits grounded in recognised theoretical frameworks. Making sure that everyone is aware of the issues that need to be resolved is the goal.

- 2) Challenges and roadblocks encountered during DEA operations can be further explored in order to minimise issues and develop alternative solutions.
- 3) One way to show appreciation for the participants' zeal is to organise follow-up main training sessions.

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